

Quantitative gravimetric estimation :

Under the above mentioned conditions of pH, reagent concentration and temperature gravimetric estimations of different quantities of Au(III) were done. The conversion factor for complex to metal is 0.3376.

Effect of foreign ions :

There was no interference by the addition of different quantities of foreign ions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CH_3COO^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cd^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Hg^{+2}) on the precipitation of Au(III) done in suitable conditions.

There are certain cations like Fe(III), Cu(II), Pt(IV) which interfered in the estimation of Au(III).

In the light of above facts reagent DEAPG may be recommended as a promising gravimetric reagent for gold(III).

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Paper and Cellulose Thin Layer Chromatography of Toxic Cations

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CLEAR separations of toxic cations¹⁻⁵ :—Ce(IV), Ni(II), Cu(II), Bi(III), Hg(II), Tl(I), Pb(II), Be(II) and As(V) were achieved by ascending paper and cellulose thin layer chromatography in solvents: (1) Ethyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : methyl ethyl ketone : chloroform : 12N. HCl (25 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 10); (2) Ethyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : chloroform : methyl ethyl ketone : 12N. HCl (20 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 15) and (3) Isopropyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : acetone : chloroform : 12N. HCl (25 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 10). The order of R_f values is : $\text{Hg} > \text{As} > \text{Bi} > \text{Cu} > \text{Pb} > \text{Ni} > \text{Ce} > \text{Be}$, Tl. The differential mobility and separation of cations is based on differential solubilization of their chlorocomplexes in these polar solvents.

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Maleianilic Acids as Derivatives for Characterization of Aromatic Primary Amines and Their Paper Chromatographic Detection and Separation

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AROMATIC primary amines were characterized in qualitative analysis by formation of corresponding maleianilic acids as derivatives. The maleianilic acids were obtained in pure state and in good yield and have sharp melting points. The corresponding maleianilic acids were detected and separated using paper chromatography. The coloured spots were clearly visible while rest were visualized in iodine vapours.

Subba Rao characterized some aromatic primary amines as a derivative of corresponding phthalanilic